

Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) for the Longest Path Problem

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Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) for the Longest Path Problem

Abstract—This work presents the application of the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm to solve the Longest Path Problem in undirected cyclic graphs. The algorithm was adapted to maximize the total path cost between two vertices, with experiments conducted on graphs containing up to 100 vertices. The results indicate that ACO is effective in finding near-optimal solutions within a small number of iterations, demonstrating good scalability and exploration capability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Longest Path Problem in undirected cyclic graphs consists of finding the path with the maximum total cost between two vertices, subject to constraints such as avoiding repeated vertices and cycles. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) was chosen to solve this problem due to its bio-inspired behavior, which simulates how ants search for food using pheromone trails to guide collective decision-making.

The solution was implemented in Python, with parameter adjustments including pheromone evaporation rate, number of ants, and heuristic influence factors (ALPHA and BETA).

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The objective of the Longest Path Problem is to maximize the total cost C between two vertices v_s (start) and v_f (end) in a graph $G = (V, E)$, where V represents the set of vertices and E the set of weighted edges. The problem formulation is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximize: } C &= \sum_{(i,j) \in P} w_{ij} \\ \text{Subject to:} & \\ (1) \text{ Each vertex is visited at most once;} & \\ (2) \text{ The path starts at vertex } v_s \text{ and ends at vertex } v_f; & \\ (3) \text{ Cycles are not allowed.} & \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

III. METHODOLOGY

The ACO algorithm was adapted to address the Longest Path Problem. Ants iteratively construct paths through the graph, depositing pheromone on edges based on solution quality. Over successive iterations, high-quality paths are reinforced while inferior paths gradually lose influence due to pheromone evaporation, allowing the algorithm to converge toward optimal or near-optimal solutions.

A. Main Modifications

The following adaptations were implemented:

- **Subcycle Prevention:** A validation mechanism was applied to prevent revisiting previously visited vertices, ensuring valid paths without cycles.
- **Adjusted Evaporation Rate:** The pheromone evaporation rate was set to 0.07, balancing exploration of new paths and exploitation of high-quality solutions.
- **Euclidean Distance Calculation:** Edge weights were computed using the Euclidean distance formula:

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \quad (2)$$

- **File Input Using *Pandas*:** Input data were loaded using the *Pandas* library, supporting both *CSV* and *TXT* formats.

B. Parameter Settings

The final parameter configuration used in the experiments is summarized below:

- **Number of Ants (N_ANTS):** 40 Determines how many ants explore the solution space. A larger number increases exploration at the cost of higher computational time.
- **Maximum Number of Iterations (MAX_ITER):** 500 Limits the total number of iterations, controlling the execution time of the algorithm.
- **Evaporation Rate (EVAPORATION_RATE):** 0.07 Controls how quickly pheromone trails decay over time.
- **Alpha (ALPHA):** 1.0 Defines the influence of pheromone trails on path selection.
- **Beta (BETA):** 8.0 Defines the influence of heuristic information (edge cost), prioritizing more promising paths.
- **Initial Pheromone (INITIAL_PHEROMONE):** 0.01 Sets the initial pheromone level on all edges, affecting early exploration behavior.

IV. RESULTS

The convergence behavior of the algorithm was analyzed over 500 iterations. The solution costs stabilized as the algorithm progressed. Figures 1, 2, and 3 illustrate convergence for three different graphs, while Figure 4 presents a visualization of the best path found for the Euclidean distance graph.

The selected parameters demonstrated strong performance, with rapid convergence toward high-quality solutions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Ant Colony Optimization proved to be an effective approach for solving the Longest Path Problem. The adapted algorithm efficiently explored the solution space and converged to high-quality solutions with reduced computational cost. The results demonstrate the scalability and robustness of ACO when applied to complex graph optimization problems.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Srinivas and K. Deb, "Multiobjective optimization using nondominated sorting in genetic algorithms," *Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 221–248, 1994.

Figure 1: Convergence for Graph 1

Figure 2: Convergence for Graph 2

Figure 3: Convergence for Graph 3

